

FACTORS OF IMPROVING CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS IN
THE PROCESS OF TEACHING THE GERMAN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: Today, the development of the creative activity of our country's students based on the requirements of the world community, the training of personnel who can freely communicate in foreign languages, as well as the wide use of the achievements of world civilization are being created, and the material and technical base is continuously being enriched, it is revealed in this monograph. "Increasing the quality and efficiency of higher education institutions based on the introduction of international educational standards and assessment of the quality of education" was set as a priority task. As a result, the possibility of teaching languages integrated into subjects is expanding in higher education institutions.

Keywords: factors, improving, creative activity, students, process, teaching, German language

Globalization and integration processes in the field of education in the 21st century imply the emergence of new approaches to the organization of the educational process in higher educational institutions. Integration processes in education mainly determine the current state of teaching foreign languages, help to revise its content. Therefore, in the process of introducing new standards, studying the content of education at the university becomes especially relevant.

It should be noted that the content of the training usually means a set of educational tasks, information and exercises that ensure the acquisition of certain knowledge and practical skills, as well as the formation of important professional characteristics of the student.

As the content of teaching any subject is determined by the goals set by the society at each stage of its socio-economic and cultural development, we consider it appropriate to dwell on the modern interpretation of teaching foreign languages.

The purpose of teaching foreign languages in higher education institutions is to acquire the language in practice, at the same time, to develop a student who is able to live and create in the changing world, to be competitive, to join the world community. These abilities are formed in the process of mastering different types of competences: linguistic, communicative, cultural and methodological, they are interrelated.

Teaching a foreign language, like any other subject, if the foundations of teaching are based on certain rules derived from basic laws, it is a direct means of student formation and contributes to the goal of didactics - constant and conscious mastering of its content. By learning a foreign language, students acquire the ability to analyze, generalize, specialize, distinguish between necessary and sufficient conditions, define concepts, make judgments, and find ways to solve given educational tasks. All this helps students to develop their monologic and dialogic speech skills, the indicators of thinking development are clarity, precision, order, reasonableness, brevity, and consistency.

Learning a language requires a lot of effort and time from every student. Educational work skills acquired at the same time give us the opportunity to effectively master the skills of performing other types of work, and the ability to do any job well requires great effort and responsibility. When properly taught, students develop observation, attention, concentration, initiative, and persistence. Teaching a foreign language increases mental activity, makes students think about their activities throughout the lesson, how to maintain interest in the studied material.

The main goal of teaching a foreign language in higher education institutions is communication. The formation of communicative competence, the ability to get enough information when reading foreign language texts, the ability to understand

the interlocutor, at the same time, the ability to express one's opinion, point of view, orally and in writing, are part of the student's active creative activity.

According to some scholars, the components of the educational content are knowledge of a certain language material (grammar, phonetics, vocabulary, spelling), topics for reading, texts, skills, competences, speaking, language concepts that do not exist in the native language. understood. At the same time, the content of education is considered as a complex dialectical unit formed by the interaction of a certain method of educational material (subject content) and the teaching process.

For a long time in didactics, the content of education was considered mainly in connection with subjects that study the basics of science. This partially explains the lack of a single approach to defining the components of the educational content in the foreign language teaching methodology and reveals the conflict of the issue of the components of the educational content. Nevertheless, components such as linguistic knowledge, material, skills and competences, topics, texts, and linguistic concepts that are not specific to the mother tongue appear in many classifications of educational content.

It is known that language material, its assimilation is the basis for the development of not only oral speech and reading skills, but also based on various linguistic materials, but also in the form of texts or sound texts in graphic design. is also formed on the basis of consistent integrity. Therefore, the texts on the topic related to the content of the training are legally included.

Nowadays, the issue of knowledge and skills is solved a little differently. First, it should be noted that the main units of content for a foreign language with oral communication are types of speech activity: in writing (letter); expressing speech in oral form (speaking); listening comprehension (listening); perception and understanding (reading) of written speech, texts. Each type of speech is based on knowledge, skills, and is used as a complex and specific creative skill system aimed at solving various communication problems.

In the process of learning a foreign language, students improve their skills, that is, their speech skills (listening, speaking, reading, understanding, etc.), and the use of vocabulary. All of the above is undoubtedly included in the content of a foreign language, because it is the basis for achieving the practical goal of teaching a foreign language. Also, the content of teaching a foreign language should be understood as linguistic materials (lexical, spelling, phonetic, grammatical), audio texts, topics, traditional spelling texts, language concepts that are not specific to the student's native language.

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